

DECISION MAKING FOR CAR SELECTION IN VIETNAM

Do Duc Trung✉

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering¹
doductrung@hau.edu.vn

Dung Hoang Tien

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering¹

Nguyen Hoai Son

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering¹

¹*Hanoi University of Industry*

298 Cau Dien str., Bac Tu Liem District, Hanoi, Vietnam, 100000

✉Corresponding author

Abstract

Mid-priced cars (segment B) are attracting the attention of middle-income families in Vietnam. They often consider choosing one of three vehicles from three different manufacturers, consisting of Hyundai Accent 1.4AT, Toyota Vios 1.5G, and Honda City 1.5L. This study was carried out to rank those three cars. Twelve criteria for rating each car provided by the dealer were used. These criteria are both qualitative and quantitative, and also fall into all three types, including max, min and another («Yes», «No»). The importance of each criterion was determined by experts in a survey. They are all knowledgeable about cars. Two multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) methods including *R* (A simple ranking method for multi-attribute decision making in the industrial environment) and CURLI (Collaborative Unbiased Rank List Integration) method were applied for ranking. This is the first work that has used both methods mentioned above. The result revealed that the rank of the alternatives is the same when both the methods were used. This result gives us a certain confidence when choosing a car. Accordingly, Honda City 1.5L is ranked first. *R* and CURLI not only succeeded in ranking cars in this study, but also promise to be successful when used in other situations. Moreover, other criteria for evaluating the vehicle options that have not been surveyed in this study are mentioned in the last section of this paper. They need to be further considered to include in other next studies for car selection.

Keywords: Multi Criteria Decision Making, B-segment car selection, R method, CURLI method.

DOI: 10.21303/2461-4262.2022.002505

1. Introduction

The demand of purchasing a car for families in Vietnam is remarkably high as the population size is nearly 100 million people. According to the data of the General Statistics Office (under the Ministry of Industry and Trade of Vietnam), currently, there are 16 cars per 1000 inhabitants in Vietnam [1]. Although the economy was greatly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, there were more than 400,000 cars registered in 2020 [2], 410,000 cars in 2021 [3], over 51,000 cars in the first four months of 2022 [4]. Thus, it can be said that the need of buying a car is increasing in Vietnam. Among the many types of cars on the market, consumers tend to prefer mid-priced cars (B-segment). There are three types of cars in the B-segment popular in the Vietnamese market, including Hyundai Accent 1.4AT, Toyota Vios 1.5G, and Honda City 1.5L. The buyers often choose a certain type of car based on their use habits, the opinions of their friends or their subjective thoughts. Choosing a car also depends on a few criteria such as price, fuel consumption, number of seats in the car, etc. This may lead to inappropriate decisions. Furthermore, there are conflicting selection criteria between the vehicles. For example, the price of the Hyundai Accent 1.4AT is lower than of the Toyota Vios 1.5G, however, the fuel consumption of the Hyundai Accent 1.4AT is higher than of the Toyota Vios 1.5G [5]. This makes it difficult for the customers to choose a car. In fact, there have been cases of conflict between family members in car decision making. This study was conducted to rank the above three types of cars with the aim of being able to give a recommendation to shoppers.

The ranking of alternatives by using multiple criteria is also known as multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) [6]. Due to the necessity of multi-criteria decision making in different fields,

there are many MCDM methods proposed by researchers: MOORA [7], COPRAS (Complex PRoportional Assessment) [8], SAW (Simple Additive Weighting) [9], WASPAS (Weighted Aggregates Sum Product Assessment) [10], PIV (Proximity Indexed Value) [11], TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) [12], VIKOR (Vlsekriterijumska optimizacija i Kompromisno Resenje (in Serbian)) [13], MABAC (Multi-Attributive Border Approximation area Comparison) [14], MAIRCA (Multi Atributive Ideal-Real Com parative Analysis) [15], MARCOS (Measurement of Alternatives and Ranking according to Compromise Solution) [16], EAMR (Evaluation by an Area-based Method of Ranking) [17], PARIS (Preference Analysis for Reference Ideal Solution) [18], RAFSI (Ranking of Alternatives through Functional mapping of criterion sub-intervals into a Single Interval) [19], COCOSO (Combined Compromise Solution) [20], CODAS (COMbinative Distance-based Assessment) [21], etc. Thousands of studies applying these methods have been published in various fields. Most recently, these methods are also being heavily exploited to rank alternatives under different circumstances: Selection of robotic systems [22]; Selection of oil tankers [23]; Supplier selection in biofuel companies based on Green criteria [24]; Supplier selection in an iron and steel industry [25]; Green supplier selection [26]; Regional aircraft selection [27]; and so on. Although the implementation of each method is not the same, two important things need to be done, namely: normalizing the data and determining the weights for the criteria [7–21]. Some obstacles to applying these methods may include:

First: The data normalization method greatly affects the rank results of the alternatives [28–31]. In order to have a certain reliability of the ranking results, it is necessary to apply many methods of data normalization at the same time, then it may take a lot of time, and sometimes cause difficulties for decision makers.

Second: The weight method significantly has an impact on the rank results of the alternatives as well [32, 33]. Besides, using only mathematical methods (Entropy, AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process), MEREC (Method based on the Removal Effects of Criteria), etc.) for determining the weights for the criteria probably does not take into account the consumer's interest in the criteria. This issue is clearly inappropriate for a product that needs to be carefully considered.

Third: A serious problem might occur when the criteria are not presented in numbers (qualitative criteria). Then these methods are not applicable. The reason for this is that normalizing the data and determining the weights for the criteria by mathematical methods (Entropy, AHP, MEREC, etc.) are only done when the criteria are quantifiable.

The three obstacles in the use of MCDM methods make decision making in car selection difficult. Because qualitative criteria also influence the car rank (driving comfort, user preferences, etc.) in addition to quantitative criteria (cost, fuel consumption, etc.). In this case, it is necessary to adopt a multi-criteria decision-making method that neither normalizes the data nor defines the weights for the criteria. The *R* method [34] and the *CURLI* method [35, 36] both meet these requirements.

The *R* method was proposed in 2021 [34]. It does not require normalizing the data. In this method, the weight of the criteria needs to be determined in a special way, based on the results of ranking the priority between the criteria as well as the ranking of the alternatives considering each criterion. Determining the weights for the criteria using the *R* method is also found to be simpler than other methods, such as the *BWM* method, *LBWA* (Level Based Weight Assessment) method or the *FUCOM* (FULL CONSISTENT METHOD) method [25]. The *R* method is probably suitable to be used for multi-criteria decision making if the criteria are in both quantitative and qualitative form. This research presents more details about it. The method is applied in a number of cases, such as: Ranking suppliers, industrial robots, material for the manufacture of an industrial product, and flexible production systems [34]; Selection for industrial robots, turning process, and bridge construction options [37]; Apart from that, there have not been any studies that apply the *R* method for multi-criteria decision making.

The *CURLI* method was first introduced in 2016 for the selection of applicants to a medical school [35]. Normalizing the data and determining the weights for the criteria are two tasks that were not required for the use of this method. Hence, it is likely suitable to be used for multi-criteria decision making if the criteria can be both quantitative and qualitative. This research presents more details about it in the following part. The *CURLI* method was found to be as effective as the

PEG (Pareto-Edgeworth Grierson) method and better than the PSI (Preference Selection Index) method as it was applied to multi-criteria decision making for the turning process [36]. Apart from that, there have not been any studies that apply the CURLI method for multi-criteria decision making.

The above analysis shows that the *R* and *CURLI* method may be successful in ranking the cars if the evaluation criteria are both qualitative and quantitative. The application of these two methods in decision making has not been done in any research to date. This is the first study to do that. The following contents of this paper include: Multi-criteria decision making steps using *R* method and *CURLI* method; the use of these two methods for ranking three types of B-segment cars in Vietnam; The conclusions drawn and the work to be done in the future.

2. Materials and methods

2. 1. R method

The steps to perform the ranking of alternatives are presented by the guidance paragraphs (excluding formulas) [34]. Perhaps this is the reason why this method has not received much attention from scholars. If the paragraphs were described in the form of formulas, they would be more accessible. In this study, the conversion of the paragraphs into mathematical formulas was performed for the purpose of further elucidating the method. The steps are as follows:

Step 1: Forming a decision matrix, as shown in **Table 1**. Where *m* is the number of alternatives; *n* is the number of criteria; *i* = 1÷*m*; *j* = 1÷*n*.

Table 1
Decision matrix

No.	<i>C</i> ₁	<i>C</i> ₂	<i>C</i> _{<i>j</i>}	<i>C</i> _{<i>n</i>}
<i>A</i> ₁	<i>x</i> ₁₁	<i>x</i> ₁₂	<i>x</i> _{1<i>j</i>}	<i>x</i> _{1<i>n</i>}
<i>A</i> ₂	<i>x</i> ₂₁	<i>x</i> ₂₂	<i>x</i> _{2<i>j</i>}	<i>x</i> _{2<i>n</i>}
<i>A</i> _{<i>i</i>}	<i>x</i> _{<i>i</i>1}	<i>x</i> _{<i>i</i>2}	<i>x</i> _{<i>i</i><i>j</i>}	<i>x</i> _{<i>i</i><i>n</i>}
<i>A</i> _{<i>m</i>}	<i>x</i> _{<i>m</i>1}	<i>x</i> _{<i>m</i>2}	<i>x</i> _{<i>m</i><i>j</i>}	<i>x</i> _{<i>m</i><i>n</i>}

Step 2: Ranking the criteria based on their importance.

Step 3: Ranking the alternatives for each criterion.

Step 4: Converting the ranks into corresponding weights according to formula (1).

$$\omega^k = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2} + \dots + \frac{1}{r_k}}, \quad k = 1 \div \max(m, n), \quad (1)$$

where *r_k* is the rank value of rank *k*.

Example:

Rank 1: $\omega^{(1)} = 1/1 = 1$.

Rank 2: $\omega^{(2)} = 1/(1+1/2) = 0.6667 = 1$.

Rank 3: $\omega^{(3)} = 1/(1+1/2+1/3) = 0.6667 = 0.5455$.

Rank 4: $\omega^{(4)} = 1/(1+1/2+1/3+1/4) = 0.6667 = 0.48$; ect.

Step 5: Assigning the weights to the ranks according to formula (2).

$$\omega^{(r_k)} = \frac{\omega^{(k)}}{\sum_{k=1}^{\max(m,n)} \omega^{(k)}}, \quad k = 1 \div \max(m, n). \quad (2)$$

Ex. If *m* = 3 and *n* = 4 then $\max(m, n) = 4$. Where:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\max(m,n)} \omega^{(k)} = 1 + 0.6667 + 0.5455 + 0.48 = 2.6922,$$

$$w^{(r1)} = 1 / 2.6922 = 0.3714,$$

$$w^{(r2)} = 0.6667 / 2.6922 = 0.2476,$$

$$w^{(r3)} = 0.5455 / 2.6922 = 0.2026,$$

$$w^{(r4)} = 0.48 / 2.6922 = 0.1783.$$

Step 6: Calculating score of the alternatives based on the formula (3).

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j^{(k)} \times w_j^{(rk)}, i = 1 \div m. \quad (3)$$

Step 7: Rank the alternatives according to the value of S_i . The alternative with highest S_i is considered the best.

2. 2. CURLI method

The ranking of alternatives using the CURLI method is implemented according to the following steps [35, 36]:

Step 1. Similar to step 1 of the *R* method.

Step 2. Forming a square matrix of order m , as shown in **Table 2**. Scoring is carried out in each cell of the matrix in the following way, for example:

– in column P_1 , if A_1 is better than A_2 , the number 1 will be filled in the cell corresponding to column P_1 – row A_2 ;

– in column P_2 , if A_2 is worse than A_1 , the number –1 will be filled in the cell corresponding to column P_2 – row A_1 ;

– in column 2 where A_2 is equal to A_m , enter 0 in the cell corresponding to column P_2 – row A_m ;

– the cells of the main diagonal of the matrix (cells of $P_1-A_1, P_2-A_2, P_3-A_3, \dots$) are left blank (or: put 0).

n scoring matrices in this way need to be constructed corresponding to n criteria.

Table 2

Example of scoring matrix for each criterion

No.	P_1	P_2	...	P_m
A_1	0	–1
A_2	1	0
...	0	...
A_m	...	0	...	0

Step 3. Adding all the scoring matrices for criteria together for a new matrix, which is called the processing scoring matrix.

Step 4. The positions of rows and columns in the processing scoring matrix are changed for all cells above the main diagonal to be less than or equal to 0. Then, the alternative in row 1 is considered the best, i.e., the order of ranking the alternatives is the same as the order of the rows from top to bottom.

3. Results and discussion

3. 1. Some parameters of cars

Three cars in the B-segment of three different brands are being commonly used in Vietnam, including: Hyundai Accent 1.4AT, Toyota Vios 1.5G, and Honda City 1.5 L. They all have five seats, that is likely suitable for the families in Vietnam, especially young families with a middle income. Twelve basic parameters of each vehicle are introduced on the dealer's website, as shown in **Table 3** [5].

Table 3
Some basic parameters of cars [5]

No.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6	C_7	C_8	C_9	C_{10}	C_{11}	C_{12}
Hyundai Accent 1.4AT	540	5.8	150	1020	6	Yes	4440	1729	1470	2600	7	Yes
Toyota Vios 1.5G	570	5.7	133	1110	7	No	4425	1730	1475	2550	7	No
Honda City 1.5L	569	5.7	134	1124	6	Yes	4553	1748	1467	2600	8	No

In Table 3:

- C_1 – Cost (Million dong – Vietnamese currency);
- C_2 – Fuel consumption (litre/100 km);
- C_3 – The clearance from the undercarriage to the road surface when the vehicle is in a horizontal position, also known as the ground clearance (mm);
- C_4 – Self-weight (kg);
- C_5 – Number of airbags;
- C_6 – Automatic mode of the car air conditioning system (Yes, No);
- C_7 – Total car length (mm);
- C_8 – Total car width (mm);
- C_9 – Total car height (mm);
- C_{10} – The interior length, also known as the wheelbase (mm);
- C_{11} – The size of the LCD screen installed in a car (inches);
- C_{12} – Sunroof (Yes, No).

Among the twelve parameters mentioned:

- C_1 and C_2 are min and quantitative criteria;
- $C_3, C_4, C_5, C_7, C_8, C_9, C_{10}, C_{11}$ are max and quantitative criteria;
- C_6 and C_{12} are another criteria. For these two criteria, «Yes» means better than «No».

And they are qualitative.

The above twelve parameters are the basis for shoppers to choose a car, and they are also information for dealers to exchange with their customers.

3. 2. Application of R method

Multi-criteria decision making aims to select the most suitable vehicle according to the above criteria. For determining the importance of each criterion, a process of interviewing experts took place. Six experts were consulted, including three sales managers and three heads of technical department at car dealerships. A reliable result was obtained that all the experts put the importance of the criteria in descending order $C_1 > C_2 > C_3 > C_4 > C_5 > C_6 > C_7 > C_8 > C_9 > C_{10} > C_{11} > C_{12}$.

The decision matrix consists of the last twelve columns in **Table 3**.

The Hyundai Accent 1.4AT, Toyota Vios 1.5G, and Honda City 1.5L vehicles are marked with the alternatives A_1, A_2 , and A_3 respectively for convenience.

The rank of the alternatives for each criterion (C_1 to C_{12}) is shown in **Table 4**. Its result revealed:

- the values of C_2 at A_2 and A_3 are equal, so the two alternatives are ranked at 1.5 (the average of 1 and 2);
- the values of C_5 at A_1 and A_3 are equal, so these two alternatives are ranked at 2.5 (the average of 2 and 3);
- at A_1 and A_3 , criteria C_6 are indicated as «Yes», so these two options are ranked at 1.5 (the average of 1 and 2);
- the values of C_{10} at A_1 and A_3 are equal, then the two alternatives are ranked at 1.5 (the average of 1 and 2); the values of C_{11} at A_1 and A_2 are equal, so these two alternatives are ranked at 2.5 (the average of 2 and 3);
- at A_2 and A_3 , the criterion C_{12} is indicated as «No», so these two options are ranked at 2.5 (the average of 2 and 3).

Table 4
Ranking the alternatives for each criterion

No.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6	C_7	C_8	C_9	C_{10}	C_{11}	C_{12}
A_1	1	3	1	3	2.5	1.5	2	3	2	1.5	2.5	1
A_2	3	1.5	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	3	2.5	2.5
A_3	2	1.5	2	1	2.5	1.5	1	1	3	1.5	1	2.5

The results shown in **Table 5** are due to the conversion of the ranks to the weights according to formula (1).

Table 5
Weights converted from ranks

Rank k	k											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
w^k	1.000	0.667	0.545	0.480	0.438	0.408	0.386	0.368	0.353	0.341	0.331	0.322

The results shown in **Table 6** are due to the assignment of the weights to the ranks according to formula (2).

Table 6
Weights assigned to ranks

Rank k	k											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
$w^{(rk)}$	0.177	0.118	0.097	0.085	0.078	0.072	0.068	0.065	0.063	0.061	0.059	0.057

Based on the data in Table 6, the weights of the criteria (C_1 to C_{12}) are also equal to the weights assigned to the ranks (for example, the weight of C_1 is 0.177, the weight of C_2 is 0.118, etc.).

The S_i score is calculated for each alternative according to formula (3) and the results are shown in **Table 7**. The results of ranking the alternatives on the basis of the value of S_i are summarized in **Table 7** as well.

Table 7
 S_i score and rank of alternatives

No.	$w_j^{(k)} * w_j^{(rk)}$												S_i	Rank
	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6	C_7	C_8	C_9	C_{10}	C_{11}	C_{12}		
A_1	0.177	0.097	0.177	0.097	0.107	0.148	0.118	0.097	0.118	0.148	0.107	0.177	0.134	2
A_2	0.097	0.148	0.097	0.118	0.177	0.097	0.097	0.118	0.177	0.097	0.072	0.107	0.116	3
A_3	0.118	0.148	0.118	0.177	0.107	0.148	0.177	0.177	0.097	0.148	0.177	0.107	0.139	1
Weight	0.177	0.118	0.097	0.085	0.078	0.072	0.068	0.065	0.063	0.061	0.059	0.057	–	–

The data in **Table 7** revealed that: the first priority is the A_3 option, the second belongs to the A_1 , and the A_2 alternative is the third. That means the Honda City 1.5L is the top choice among the three vehicles surveyed, followed by the Hyundai Accent 1.4AT, and finally the Toyota Vios 1.5G.

3. 3. Application of CURLI method

A scoring matrix is built for each criterion (C_1 to C_{12}), the results obtained are shown in **Tables 8–19**.

Table 8
Scoring matrix of criterion C_1

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	-1	-1
A_2	1	0	1
A_3	1	-1	0

Table 9
Scoring matrix of criterion C_2

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	1	1
A_2	-1	0	0
A_3	-1	0	0

Table 10
Scoring matrix of criterion C_3

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	-1	-1
A_2	1	0	1
A_3	1	-1	0

Table 11
Scoring matrix of criterion C_4

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	1	1
A_2	1	0	1
A_3	-1	-1	0

Table 12
Scoring matrix of criterion C_5

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	1	0
A_2	-1	0	-1
A_3	0	1	0

Table 13
Scoring matrix of criterion C_6

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	-1	0
A_2	1	0	1
A_3	0	-1	0

Table 14
Scoring matrix of criterion C_7

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	-1	1
A_2	1	0	1
A_3	-1	-1	0

Table 15
Scoring matrix of criterion C_8

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	1	1
A_2	-1	0	1
A_3	-1	-1	0

Table 16
Scoring matrix of criterion C_9

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	1	-1
A_2	-1	0	-1
A_3	1	1	0

Table 17
Scoring matrix of criterion C_{10}

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	-1	0
A_2	1	0	1
A_3	0	-1	0

Table 18
Scoring matrix of criterion C_{11}

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	0	1
A_2	0	0	1
A_3	-1	-1	0

Table 19
Scoring matrix of criterion C_{12}

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	-1	-1
A_2	1	0	0
A_3	1	0	0

By adding the scoring matrices of each criterion (Tables 8–19), the processing scoring matrix is achieved, as shown in Table 20.

Table 20
Processing scoring matrix

No.	P_1	P_2	P_3
A_1	0	-1	1
A_2	3	0	6
A_3	-1	-6	0

Positions of rows and columns in Table 20 are changed for all cells above the main diagonal to be less than or equal to 0, then the result is presented in Table 21.

Table 21
Processing scoring matrix after changing the position of rows and columns

No.	P_3	P_1	P_2
A_3	0	-1	-6
A_1	1	0	-1
A_2	6	3	0

According to the data in Table 21, the rank result of the alternatives is: $A_3 > A_1 > A_2$. That means the Honda City 1.5L is the top choice among the three vehicles surveyed, followed by the Hyundai Accent 1.4AT, and finally the Toyota Vios 1.5G. As a consequence, the vehicle ranks using the R and CURLI method are the same. This result creates a certain confidence in decision makers. That is: the Hyundai Accent 1.4A is the first choice when buying one of these three cars.

To evaluate the effectiveness of an MCDM method, in addition to verifying that it shows the best solution, it is also necessary to test its stability under different scenarios. Two methods commonly used to generate different scenarios are changing the weights for the criteria and removing a solution from the list of solutions [38]. However, when using the CURLI method, determining the weights for the criteria is not a concern, so the method of removing a solution from the solution list will be used in this study.

The best solution (A_3) was removed from the list of solutions. Assuming no rank inversion phenomenon occurs, the ranking order of solutions is $A_1 > A_2$, this is called the perfect case. The ranking of the remaining two solutions (including A_1 and A_2) is conducted from the beginning. Fig. 1 shows the actual ranking after recalculating (R) and the ranking under perfect conditions (R^*).

The results in Fig. 1 show that the ranking results of the two solutions are completely identical between the actual condition and with the perfect condition (For both R and CURLI methods). It means that there is no ranking reversion phenomenon in any of the solutions. At this point, it is possible to firmly confirm that, in this case, the R and CURLI methods were successful in ranking the cars.

Fig. 1. Ranked results of the solutions after removing A_3 solution

However, the recommendation given above is based on only twelve criteria for car evaluation. These criteria have been made public on the website of car dealers. In fact, the choice of vehicles depends on many other factors such as consumer trends, the impact of the engine's emissions on the environment, the origin of the car, the care service of the dealers after selling, payment form (full or partial payment), engine life, vehicle maintenance service, etc. The first priority vehicle may also be changed if the number of criteria surveyed is more. Nonetheless, the car-ranking method used in this study is likely applicable.

4. Conclusions

The B-segment cars are attracting the attention of middle-income families in Vietnam. The three cars that are commonly chosen are Hyundai Accent 1.4AT, Toyota Vios 1.5G, and Honda City 1.5L. The evaluation of vehicles is carried out using twelve criteria and the ranking of the criteria importance is conducted by surveying the opinions of experts. In order to rank the vehicles, two multi-criteria decision-making methods were used, including the *R* method and the CURLI method. This is the first study to apply both methods in a multi-criteria decision problem, and also the first time to apply in car ranking. Some conclusions are drawn as follows:

- the results of ranking the cars are the same as the *R* and CURLI methods are used. This creates a certain confidence in the rank;
- the strength of the *R* and CURLI methods was also found that the ranking inversion phenomenon does not occur under any scenarios. This is the advantage of these method in comparing with many other methods. Moreover, when applied these method, it does not require the determining weights for the criteria nor require the normalizing the data, so, it is recommended to be used;
- priority for car selection decreases in order of Honda City 1.5L, Hyundai Accent 1.4AT, and Toyota Vios 1.5G. That means Honda City 1.5L is the first choice among these three vehicles;
- the application of the *R* method and the CURLI method also bring certain confidence in the rank of the alternatives if more criteria for evaluating the vehicles were used (such as consumer trends, car origin, etc.). Furthermore, these two methods are also expected to rank alternatives in other areas, especially when the criteria are qualitative.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

References

- [1] Tapchicongthuong. Available at: <https://tapchicongthuong.vn/>
- [2] <https://thanhvien.vn/nam-2020-nguoi-viet-sam-hon-400000-o-to-thuong-hieu-nao-duoc-ua-chuong-nhat-post1272928.html>
- [3] <https://thanhvien.vn/nguoi-viet-mua-sam-410-000-o-to-nam-2021-xe-han-ngay-cang-duoc-ua-chuong-post1420676.html>
- [4] <https://tienphong.vn/hon-51-000-o-to-ban-ra-trong-thang-4-tai-viet-nam-post1437822.tpo>
- [5] Hyundai Accent: giá lăn bánh, ưu đãi (10/2022). Available at: <https://giaxeoto.vn/hyundai-accent-thong-so-ky-thuat-gia-ban-320.html>
- [6] Zopounidis, C., Doumpos, M. (2017). Multiple Criteria Decision Making – Applications in Management and Engineering. Springer, 211. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-39292-9>
- [7] Brauers, W. K. (2004). Optimization methods for a stakeholder society. A revolution in economic thinking by multi-objective optimization. Springer. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9178-2>
- [8] Triantaphyllou, E. (2000). Multi-criteria Decision Making Methods: A Comparative Study. Springer, 290. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-3157-6>
- [9] Kusumadewi, S., Hartati, S., Harjoko, A., Wardoyo, R. (2006). Fuzzy Multi-Attribute Decision Making (FUZZY MADM). Yogyakarta: Penerbit Graha Ilmu.
- [10] Zavadskas, E. K., Turskis, Z., Antucheviciene, J. (2012). Optimization of Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment. Electronics and Electrical Engineering, 122 (6). doi: <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.eee.122.6.1810>
- [11] Mufazzal, S., Muzakkir, S. M. (2018). A new multi-criterion decision making (MCDM) method based on proximity indexed value for minimizing rank reversals. Computers & Industrial Engineering, 119, 427–438. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2018.03.045>

- [12] Hwang, C.-L., Lai, Y.-J., Liu, T.-Y. (1993). A new approach for multiple objective decision making. *Computers & Operations Research*, 20 (8), 889–899. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-0548\(93\)90109-v](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-0548(93)90109-v)
- [13] Opricovic, S., Tzeng, G.-H. (2004). Compromise solution by MCDM methods: A comparative analysis of VIKOR and TOPSIS. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 156 (2), 445–455. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0377-2217\(03\)00020-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0377-2217(03)00020-1)
- [14] Pamučar, D., Čirović, G. (2015). The selection of transport and handling resources in logistics centers using Multi-Attributive Border Approximation area Comparison (MABAC). *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42 (6), 3016–3028. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2014.11.057>
- [15] Pamucar, D. S., Tarle, S. P., Parezanovic, T. (2018). New hybrid multi-criteria decision-making DEMATEL-MAIRCA model: sustainable selection of a location for the development of multimodal logistics centre. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 31 (1), 1641–1665. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677x.2018.1506706>
- [16] Stević, Ž., Pamučar, D., Puška, A., Chatterjee, P. (2020). Sustainable supplier selection in healthcare industries using a new MCDM method: Measurement of alternatives and ranking according to Compromise solution (MARCOS). *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 140, 106231. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2019.106231>
- [17] Ghorabae, M. K., Zavadskas, E. K., Amiri, M., Antucheviciene, J. (2016). Evaluation by an Area-based Method of Ranking Interval Type-2 Fuzzy Sets (EAMRIT-2F) for Multi-criteria Group Decision-making. *Transformations in Business & Economics*, 15 (3), 76–95.
- [18] Ardil, C. (2020). Aircraft Selection Process Using Preference Analysis for Reference Ideal Solution (PARIS). *International Journal of Aerospace and Mechanical Engineering*, 14 (3), 80–90.
- [19] Žižović, M., Pamučar, D., Albijanić, M., Chatterjee, P., Pribičević, I. (2020). Eliminating Rank Reversal Problem Using a New Multi-Attribute Model—The RAFSI Method. *Mathematics*, 8 (6), 1015. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/math8061015>
- [20] Yazdani, M., Zarate, P., Kazimieras Zavadskas, E., Turskis, Z. (2019). A combined compromise solution (CoCoSo) method for multi-criteria decision-making problems. *Management Decision*, 57 (9), 2501–2519. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/md-05-2017-0458>
- [21] Keshavarz-Ghorabae, M., Zavadskas, E. K., Turskis, Z., Antucheviciene, J. (2016). A new combinative distance-based assessment (CODAS) method for multi-criteria decision-making. *Economic Computation and Economic Cybernetics Studies and Research*, 50 (3), 25–44.
- [22] Bairagi, B. (2022). A homogeneous group decision making for selection of robotic systems using extended TOPSIS under subjective and objective factors. *Decision Making: Applications in Management and Engineering*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31181/dmame0304052022b>
- [23] Gorcun, O. F., Senthil, S., Küçükönder, H. (2021). Evaluation of tanker vehicle selection using a novel hybrid fuzzy MCDM technique. *Decision Making: Applications in Management and Engineering*, 4 (2), 140–162. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31181/dmame210402140g>
- [24] Kazemitash, N., Fazlollahtabar, H., Abbaspour, M. (2021). Rough Best-Worst Method for Supplier Selection in Biofuel Companies based on Green criteria. *Operational Research in Engineering Sciences: Theory and Applications*, 4 (2), 1–12. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31181/oresta20402001k>
- [25] Chattopadhyay, R., Das, P. P., Chakraborty, S. (2022). Development of a Rough-MABAC-DoE-based Metamodel for Supplier Selection in an Iron and Steel Industry. *Operational Research in Engineering Sciences: Theory and Applications*, 5 (1), 20–40. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31181/oresta190222046c>
- [26] Fazlollahtabar, H., Kazemitash, N. (2021). Green supplier selection based on the information system performance evaluation using the integrated best-worst method. *Facta Universitatis, Series: Mechanical Engineering*, 19 (3), 345. doi: <https://doi.org/10.22190/fume201125029f>
- [27] Bakır, M., Akan, Ş., Özdemir, E. (2021). Regional aircraft selection with fuzzy PIPRECIA and fuzzy marcos: a case study of the Turkish airline industry. *Facta Universitatis, Series: Mechanical Engineering*, 19 (3), 423. doi: <https://doi.org/10.22190/fume210505053b>
- [28] Aytakin, A. (2021). Comparative Analysis of the Normalization Techniques in the Context of MCDM Problems. *Decision Making: Applications in Management and Engineering*, 4 (2), 1–25. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31181/dmame210402001a>
- [29] Ersoy, N. (2020). Selecting the Best Normalization Technique for ROV Method: Towards a Real Life Application. *Gazi University Journal of Science*, 34 (2), 592–609. doi: <https://doi.org/10.35378/gujs.767525>
- [30] Palczewski, K., Sałabun, W. (2019). Influence of various normalization methods in PROMETHEE II: an empirical study on the selection of the airport location. *Procedia Computer Science*, 159, 2051–2060. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.09.378>
- [31] Miranda Lakshmi, T., Prasanna Venkatesan, V. (2014). A Comparison of Various Normalization in Techniques for Order Performance by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). *International Journal of Computing Algorithm*, 3 (3), 255–259. doi: <https://doi.org/10.20894/ijcoa.101.003.003.023>

- [32] Do, T. (2021). Application of TOPSIS and PIV Methods for Multi – Criteria Decision Making in Hard Turning Process. *Journal of Machine Engineering*, 21 (4), 57–71. doi: <https://doi.org/10.36897/jme/142599>
- [33] Gunantara, N. (2018). A review of multi-objective optimization: Methods and its applications. *Cogent Engineering*, 5 (1), 1502242. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311916.2018.1502242>
- [34] Rao, R. V., Lakshmi, J. (2021). R-method: A simple ranking method for multi-attribute decision-making in the industrial environment. *Journal of Project Management*, 6, 223–230. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.jpm.2021.5.001>
- [35] Kiger, J. R., Annibale, D. J. (2016). A new method for group decision making and its application in medical trainee selection. *Medical Education*, 50 (10), 1045–1053. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.13112>
- [36] Duc Trung, D. (2022). Multi-criteria decision making of turning operation based on PEG, PSI and CURLI methods. *Manufacturing Review*, 9, 9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1051/mfreview/2022007>
- [37] Trung, D. D. (2022). Comparison r and curli methods for multi-criteria decision making. *Advanced Engineering Letters*, 1 (2), 46–56. doi: <https://doi.org/10.46793/adeletters.2022.1.2.3>
- [38] Pamucar, D., Bozanic, D., Randjelovic, A. (2017). Multi-criteria decision making: An example of sensitivity analysis. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 12 (1), 1–27. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5937/sjm12-9464>

Received date 22.07.2022

Accepted date 20.09.2022

Published date 29.11.2022

© The Author(s) 2022

This is an open access article
under the Creative Commons CC BY license

How to cite: Trung, D. D., Tien, D. H., Son, N. H. (2022). Decision making for car selection in Vietnam. *EUREKA: Physics and Engineering*, 6, 139–150. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21303/2461-4262.2022.002505>